

Teachers' worklife, mental health, and job burnout: Cases of Thailand and Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to: i) explore the worklife areas, mental health, and job burnout among Thai and Indonesian teachers; ii) investigate the roles of worklife areas on mental health and burnout; and iii) compare the two groups of teachers. The participants consisted of 340 teachers (210 Thai teachers and 130 Indonesian teachers) who voluntarily responded to the online questionnaire. The instruments for data collection included the depression anxiety stress scales-21, the areas of worklife survey, and the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey. Frequency, mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation coefficient, and multiple regression analysis were utilized to analyze the data. The results revealed that the mean scores for six areas of worklife were comparable across the two groups, whereas the mean scores for mental health and job burnout were distinct. In addition, it was discovered that teachers' worklife could predict their mental health and job burnout in Thailand and Indonesia. However, the predictive patterns varied for each scale of mental health and burnout, as well as across the two groups. The study's findings shed light on the impacts of workplace factors on teachers' mental well-being.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is one of the most demanding professions. Teachers, regardless of school level, are confronted with challenging events on a regular basis that require a strong psychological and physical commitment [1]. The challenging demands, such as a heavy workload, long working hours, a large class size, poor working facilities, role ambiguity, and inadequate job resources have a substantial effect on teachers' mental health [2], particularly in promoting the emergence of disorder and symptoms associated with anxiety, depression, stress, and burnout [1].

The interaction between teacher and student, while beneficial for teaching, may also cause emotionally exhausting and discouraging for teachers [3]. A growing body of evidence suggests that mental health problems can demotivate teachers, diminish their job efficiency, and lead to their resignation. Teachers who are depressed may not be able to establish a creative teaching environment that encourages students to learn and acquire new skills, while those who are stressed are more likely to be absent, early retire, and leave the profession [4]. For example, a survey of 2,588 teachers from 46 Texas schools, the results demonstrated that teachers with low mental health quality, high stress levels, depression, panic disorder, and anxiety disorder had a high tendency to quit their job [5].

Multiple studies suggest that many teachers throughout the world are struggling with mental health difficulties, including stress, depression, and anxiety [6]–[8]. For example, the study of the sixth wave of the European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS) which collected data from various occupations across Europe revealed that despite the fact that teaching professionals reported higher levels of job satisfaction than other professionals, they also experienced higher levels of stress, anxiety, fatigue, and sleeping problems [9]. In accordance with the findings of research on the mental health of secondary school teachers in Hong Kong, 30.3% of teachers had the greatest degree of anxiety and 12.3% had the highest level of depression [10]. Regardless of the percentage, the high levels of anxiety and depression among teachers have a significant impact on their teaching performance.

According to the data from upper secondary schools in Stockholm, teachers' stress, fatigue, and depression had a strong and consistent negative correlation with students' school satisfaction and perceived teacher caring [11]. This finding raises a serious concern for the mental health of teachers. Importantly, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers throughout the globe have been compelled to significantly change, especially in their teaching methods and lifestyles. Such a rapid transition increases mental health problems with lasting consequences. For example, when teachers returned to schools and universities in Spain during the COVID-19 pandemic, their mental health issues revealed that a substantial percentage of them still suffered from stress, depression, and anxiety; this result indicated a greater proportion of teachers suffering from mental health issues than before the pandemic [12].

Burnout has long been recognized as a stress-related issue, particularly for occupations that involve people [3], especially in the teaching profession. Teachers are burdened by the several roles and demands placed upon them by others; hence, teachers frequently feel that they are not fulfilling all of their obligations sufficiently, resulting in emotional fatigue and burnout symptoms [2]. A number of evidence suggest that job stress is a predictor of job inefficiency, family-relationship problems, and bad health, and these findings are consistent with those of job burnout [13].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), burnout is considered an occupational phenomenon resulting from unmanageable "chronic workplace stress" that manifests in three forms: exhaustion, negativism, and diminished professional efficacy [14]. Along the lines of the definition provided by Maslach, Leiter, and Schaufeli [15], burnout is a psychological syndrome that develops as a sustained response to chronic interpersonal challenges at work, and the three essential components of this response are extreme exhaustion, feelings of cynicism and disengagement from the job, and a sense of ineffectiveness and lack of achievement. Burnout has been evident to be negatively associated with psychological and physical well-being [3], self-efficacy and job satisfaction [16].

Several risk factors contribute to teacher burnout, for example, workplace context (e.g., inadequate resources, excessive workload, job pressures, deficiency of professional recognition), educational settings (e.g., students' behavior problems, lack of student motivation, school environment, relationships with colleagues), and teachers' characteristics that influence their propensity to burnout (such as self-control, personality, self-esteem) [1]. However, a substantial body of research points to work-related burnout as the major cause [17]. According to Maslach [18], individuals with high levels of emotional exhaustion are more likely to experience an excessive workload; those with high levels of cynicism or depersonalization do not experience work overload, but rather a disengage with the organization, its members, culture, or values; and those with low profession efficacy tend to produce unsatisfactory and ineffective work.

Leiter and Maslach [19] reviewed the organizational risk factors associated with job stress and burnout, including workload, control, reward, community, fairness, and values. These six factors reflect the areas of job-person mismatch—the larger the perceived difference between the person and the job, the higher the probability of burnout [19], [20]. In this model, workload refers to the quantity of tasks to be completed in a certain period of time; control refers to the freedom to make decisions, solve issues, and assume responsibilities on the job; reward involves money, social, and intrinsic rewards corresponding with the contributions of individuals; community is the degree of social support in the workplace; fairness is the constancy and equality of rules applied to all members of the organization; and values refer to what is essential to the workplace and its members [20]. It is important to note that understanding the factors that contribute to teacher burnout is crucial for building schools that promote teachers' work satisfaction and the delivery of high-quality education [21]. Thus, the focus of the current research is to explore the workplace environment as a factor influencing teachers' mental health and job burnout.

Although a substantial amount of evidence suggests that organizational factors have a significant effect on teachers' mental health and burnout, research on this topic in Thailand and Indonesia remains scarce. In particular, during the COVID-19 pandemic, Thai and Indonesian teachers faced an increase in job demands as a result of school closures and the transition to virtual or online-offline education; yet inadequate study has been undertaken on Thai and Indonesian teachers' mental health concerns and job burnout. Based on the literature review, it was recognized that there was a need for a more extensive study on worklife factors and its relationships with any dimension of the mental health and burnout of Thai and Indonesian

teachers. For this reason, the current study aimed to analyze the worklife areas, mental health, and job burnout of Thai and Indonesian teachers; to investigate the effects of worklife areas on mental health and burnout; and to compare the two groups of teachers. By gaining a clearer understanding of the individual predicted relationships between worklife areas and teachers' mental health and burnout, the results of this study may help to bridge the existing knowledge gap in Thailand and Indonesia. Understanding how each worklife factor affects any dimension of teachers' mental health and burnout will enable Thai and Indonesian administrators and policy makers to focus more on teachers' mental health problems and burnout, to better prepare for preventing teachers' resignation, and to provide the most effective job resources to motivate teachers to perform at their highest level.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study was approved by the Ethics Review Committee of Mahasarakham University (No. 005/2021). Due to the fact that the data was obtained during the COVID-19 pandemic, the researchers decided to use a convenience sample technique to recruit participants and collect their responses using an online questionnaire. Teachers were invited through social media to voluntarily participate in the study. The teachers who responded voluntarily to an online questionnaire granted informed consent using online forms. The data collection was administered in Thailand and Indonesia between December 2021 and March 2022 and December 2021 and May 2022, respectively. The participants consisted of 340 primary and high school teachers (210 Thai teachers and 130 Indonesian teachers). They were asked to self-assess their perception of worklife (workload, control, reward, community, fairness, and values), mental health (depression, anxiety, and stress), and job burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization or cynicism, and personal accomplishment). Demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants (Thailand: n=210 and Indonesia: n=130)

	Teaching levels	Gender				Total	%
		Male	%	Female	%		
Thailand	Primary school	13	6.19	90	42.86	103	49.00
	High school	16	7.62	74	35.23	90	42.90
	Primary and high school	3	1.43	14	6.67	17	8.10
	Total	32	15.24	178	84.76	210	100.00
Indonesia	Primary school	18	13.85	48	36.92	66	50.77
	Junior high school	10	7.69	29	22.31	39	30.00
	High school	9	6.92	16	12.31	25	19.20
	Total	37	28.46	93	71.54	130	100.00

The instruments involved the depression, anxiety, stress scale-21 (DASS-21), the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Scale (MBI-ES), and the Areas of Worklife Scale (AWS) in Thai and Indonesian languages. The DASS-21 was developed by Lovibond and Lovibond [22] as a self-report to measure the emotional states of depression, anxiety, and stress. The scale has been widely used and translated into several languages, including Thai and Indonesian. The DASS-21 in Thai translation was provided by the National Centre in human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) Epidemiology and Clinical Research in Sydney, Australia, while the Indonesian translation was carried out by Evelina Damanik. Both translation versions can be obtained from the DASS website (<http://www2.psy.unsw.edu.au/groups/dass/>).

The DASS-21 is a short version of the original, 42-items scale. The DASS-21 consisted of seven items for depression, seven items for anxiety, and seven items for stress. The participants were asked to indicate how much they agree with the statement on a 4-point Likert scale (0=did not apply to me at all, 1=applied to me to some degree, or some for the time, 2=applied to me to a considerable degree or a good part of time, 3=applied to me very much or most of the time). According to Lovibond and Lovibond [22], the sum score of each subscale on the DASS-21 needs to be multiplied by two in order for the final score to be equated to the DASS normative data. Thus, the range of each subscale's total score after multiplication by two was 0 to 42. Each subscale interpreted differently, for example, at a normal level, depression scores ranged from 0 to 9, anxiety scores from 0 to 7, and stress scores from 0 to 14 see also [22]. For the Thai scale, the Cronbach's alphas were as: depression .886, anxiety .839, and stress .836, whereas for the Indonesian scale, they were depression .889, anxiety .871, and stress .857.

The Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Scale (MBI-ES) was used to assess teachers' job burnout with three subscales: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment. The scale was translated into Thai and Indonesian languages and then back translated into English to validate the language accuracy. The MBI-ES for Thai participants comprised 22 items (emotional exhaustion nine items,

depersonalization five items, and personal accomplishment 8 items), whereas that for Indonesian participants contained 21 items (emotional exhaustion nine items, depersonalization four items, and personal accomplishment eight items). The MBI-ES in both Thai and Indonesian were a 7-point Likert scale indicating the degree in which teachers agree with the statement (0=never, 1=a few times a year or less, 2=once a month or less, 3=a few times a month, 4=once a week, 5=a few times a week, and 6=every day). The Thai MBI-ES had alpha values of .951, .837, and .760 for emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment, respectively. The Cronbach's alpha values for the Indonesian MBI-ES were as: emotional exhaustion .923, depersonalization .843, and personal accomplishment .938.

The AWS developed by Leiter and Maslach [20] is a standard scale that is widely used by scholars around the world. The scale was employed to assess teachers' congruence with the work environment in six subscales: workload, control, reward, community, fairness, and values. The scale was translated into Thai and Indonesian and then back translated into English for the language accuracy check. The Thai AWS involved 25 items (workload four items, control four items, reward three items, community five items, fairness five items, and values four items), and the Indonesian AWS consisted of 26 items (workload four items, control four items, reward four items, community four items, fairness six items, and values four items). The Thai and Indonesian versions of the AWS were a 5-point Likert scale indicating the degree in which teachers agree with the statement (1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=hard to decide, 4=agree, and 5=strongly agree). The reliability of the Thai AWS for workload, control, reward, community, fairness, and values presented alpha values of .838, .890, .738, .806, .885, and .865, respectively. The Cronbach's alphas for the Indonesian AWS were as: workload .777, control .880, reward .713, community .934, fairness .845, and values .899. Frequency, mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation coefficient, and forward multiple regression analysis were used to examine the obtained data.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The worklife mean scores of Thai and Indonesian teachers followed comparable trends. To a certain extent, the mean scores for control, reward, community, and values were considered to be average, while the mean scores for workload and fairness were moderately high. As the mean scores in both groups for all subscales of worklife areas are higher than the midpoint (3.00), it suggests that Thai and Indonesian teachers recognize the congruence between their preferences and the workplace [20]. It is possible that teachers in Thailand and Indonesia have participated in teacher professional development processes which may prepare individuals for their roles, obligations, and duties as teachers and within the educational system. As a consequence, Thai and Indonesian teachers are ready to set expectations in line with the actual work environment.

As presented in Table 2, Thai teachers have the highest mean score in the community (\bar{x} = 3.90). It reflects on the social climate in the school that fosters pleasant emotions, teamwork support, and friendship. For Indonesia, the reward has the highest mean score (\bar{x} = 3.92), indicating that teachers perceive a fit between their expectations and external reinforcement (e.g., compensation), social reinforcement (e.g., recognition for completing important tasks), and intrinsic rewards (e.g., a sense of pride for accomplishing something significant and well) [20].

Table 2. Mean values and standard deviations for Thailand and Indonesian teachers

Variables	Thailand (n=210)		Indonesia (n=130)	
	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD
Areas of worklife				
Workload range: 1-5	3.18	0.89	3.38	0.60
Control range: 1-5	3.78	0.80	3.63	1.06
Reward range: 1-5	3.51	0.92	3.92	0.75
Community range: 1-5	3.90	.059	3.87	1.06
Fairness range: 1-5	3.14	0.75	3.42	0.61
Values range: 1-5	3.84	0.67	3.54	1.07
Mental health				
Stress range: 0-42	12.37	7.76	9.15	7.47
Anxiety range: 0-42	7.16	7.22	6.20	6.79
Depression range: 0-42	5.85	6.96	4.15	5.33
Burnout				
Emotional exhaustion range: 0-6	1.97	1.45	1.05	1.18
Depersonalization range: 0-6	0.85	1.07	0.67	0.98
Personal accomplishment range: 0-6	4.45	1.05	3.94	1.63

Regarding mental health, the researchers followed the DASS–21 scoring instructions [22]. To be precise, the score for each subscale was computed by adding the relevant item scores together and then multiplying by two for the final score. Hence, the scores range from 0 and 42. As shown in Table 2, Thai and Indonesian teachers have the same pattern of mean scores, with stress having the highest mean score ($\bar{x}=12.37$ for Thai teachers, $\bar{x}=9.15$ for Indonesian teachers) and depression having the lowest mean score ($\bar{x}=5.58$ for Thai teachers, $\bar{x}=4.15$ for Indonesian teachers). Based on the DASS–21 scoring guideline [22], the mean scores indicate that both Thai and Indonesian teachers experienced normal levels of stress and depression. However, Thai teachers reported a mild level of anxiety, whereas Indonesian teachers reported a normal level. This might be the reason that the time of data collection in Thailand occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic which there is still confusion regarding education policies and procedures in educational settings.

Such unpredictability and uncertainty have a harmful effect on a variety of factors, including mental health issues. It is evident that most individuals do not desire to be aware of the hazards they may encounter in the future, but rather wish to be aware of and manage the threats they experience today [23]. A person's anxiety, stress and depression originate from a lack of control over future harmful circumstances and an inability to cope with mental challenges [24]. Consequently, teachers in Thailand are rather concerned. In Indonesia, the data collection was administered from December 2021 to May 2022. According to United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund or UNICEF's report on the COVID-19 situation in Indonesia, the government issued new regulations enabling face-to-face education in schools in December 2021, and as of March 2022, 96% of all schools were still utilizing face-to-face instruction under security protocols [25]. This report indicates that the working circumstances for teachers in Indonesia are quite stable. This may help teachers in Indonesia feel more at ease in their professional and personal lives. Therefore, all aspects of mental health were at normal levels.

This result is consistent with the findings of a study of teachers at five public schools in Thailand, which revealed that teachers had the highest mean scores on stress [4], though it is considered a normal level. Moreover, investigations undertaken in a variety of countries had similar results [1], [2], [6]. This may be related to the fact that the teaching profession faces several challenges, such as a shortage of teaching resources, the pressure to assume various duties, interpersonal issues, and student high-achievement standards [20]. Such challenges that teachers face on a daily basis may cause them to feel less at ease and less patient, but not to the point of suffering, despondency, and unhappiness with life [22]. Furthermore, the data for this study were collected during the COVID-19 pandemic, which has resulted in life and career insecurity among Thai and Indonesian teachers.

Teachers in both groups may acquire "intolerance of uncertainty," a condition characterized by a negative attitude toward uncertainty. Individuals interpret ambiguous data with prejudice. An unclear circumstance is perceived as a threat [26]. These beliefs and actions lead to nervousness, heightened anxiety, and danger perception [27]. However, it appears that stress and depression among Thai and Indonesian teachers are still normal, but anxiety of Thai teachers are mild level. This may be due to the fact that the data collection was administered at the period when traditional teaching methods were reestablished in Thailand and Indonesia. Additionally, regular classes and the intensity of the COVID-19 pandemic have been drastically diminished. This may assist both groups of teachers feel more at ease at work.

In terms of job burnout, it was discovered that the MBI score profile of teachers in Thailand fell into an engaged profile (low level of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, and high level of personal accomplishment). Despite the fact that the mean scores of Indonesian teachers on all subscales of burnout were inconsistent with the engaged profile, their score on personal accomplishment was relatively close to the high level. As a result, it is assumed that the MBI profile of Indonesian teachers reflected an engagement as well. This profile suggests that despite the fact that teaching is a very demanding profession, both groups of teachers were able to manage fatigue and negative emotions, as well as execute teaching obligations and other assigned efficiently.

The worklife areas and burnout data interestingly indicate that teachers in Thailand and Indonesia have a moderate level of workload, a high level of job control and rewards, and an engaged profile of the MBI scores. According to Bakker *et al.* [28], if job resources are abundant in the working environment, and the negative impacts of job demands that lead to exhaustion and cynicism are mitigated. Consistent with the findings of Bottiani *et al.* [29], teachers with strong self-efficacy, excellent connections with colleagues and students had low levels of stress and job burnout. In addition, increasing job resources might reduce teachers' stress and exhaustion that contribute to undesirable behavioral problems of students. Whereas both groups of teachers regarded the job requirements at an average level, the perception of job control and rewards, which were considered as the job resources, were high. Thus, the teachers in both groups scored similarly on the engaged profile of burnout.

Table 3 displays the relationships between Thai teachers' worklife, mental health, and job burnout. With a statistically significance of .01, the mental health in all three dimensions is positively related to emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, but negatively correlated to professional achievement. All six areas of worklife are found to be negatively correlated with stress, anxiety, depression, exhaustion, and depersonalization at a statistically significant level of .01, with the exception of the associations between workload and depersonalization, and between fairness and anxiety, which are both statistically significant at .05. It suggests that the more that Thai teachers perceive a congruence between their workplace and their expectations about job demands, control over work, rewards, social interaction at work, fairness, and values, the less that they experience stress, anxiety, depression, emotional exhaustion, and depersonalization. In addition, four factors of worklife-control, rewards, community and values-positively related to personal accomplishment with a statistical significance of .01. It implies that Thai teachers' performance improves when their expectations for control, rewards, community, and values are more aligned with their workplace.

Table 3. Correlation analysis for each dimension of variables (Thailand)

	WL	CON	REW	COM	FAIR	VAL	ST	ANX	DEP	EE	DP	PA
WL	1											
CON	.270**	1										
REW	.436**	.257**	1									
COM	.260**	.506**	.560**	1								
FAIR	.410**	.247**	.394**	.434**	1							
VAL	.136*	.500**	.201**	.481**	.461**	1						
ST	-.296**	-.388**	-.269**	-.278**	-.201**	-.226**	1					
ANX	-.180**	-.363**	-.262**	-.364**	-.152*	-.252**	.793**	1				
DEP	-.191**	-.429**	-.366**	-.396**	-.262**	-.334**	.752**	.814**	1			
EE	-.407**	-.438**	-.340**	-.389**	-.407**	-.393**	.628**	.558**	.604**	1		
DP	-.170**	-.282**	-.296**	-.399**	-.271**	-.338**	.544**	.574**	.633**	.685**	1	
PA	.101	.412**	.271**	.389**	.106	.275**	-.222**	-.272**	-.359**	-.194**	-.289**	1

Workload (WL), Control (CON), Reward (REW), Community (COM), Fairness (FAIR), Values (VAL), Stress (ST), Anxiety (ANX), Depression (DEP), Emotional exhaustion (EE), Depersonalization (DP), Professional achievement (PA)

As shown in Table 4, significant correlations are found among worklife, mental health, and job burnout in Indonesian sample. To be extent, all three dimensions of mental health are significantly positively associated with emotional exhaustion and depersonalization at .01 level. Only anxiety is negatively related to professional achievement with statistical significance of .05. All six areas of worklife are associated with mental health and burnout, although the strength of these relationships varies. Notably, reward is negatively correlated with stress, anxiety, depression, emotional exhaustion, and depersonalization, while positively related to professional achievement at a statistically significant level of .01. This suggests that teachers in Indonesia who perceive a high level of congruence between their expectations and their work environment regarding intrinsic and extrinsic rewards experience less stress, anxiety, depression, emotional tiredness, and depersonalization, but greater professional efficacy. Control has a positive connection only with professional achievement at a statistically significant level of .01. The data also show that workload is correlated with depression and emotional exhaustion; community is related to anxiety, exhaustion, and efficacy; fairness is associated with stress, anxiety, depression, exhaustion, and professional efficacy; and value is correlated with anxiety and professional achievement.

Table 4. Correlation analysis for each dimension of variables (Indonesia)

	WL	CON	REW	COM	FAIR	VAL	ST	ANX	DEP	EE	DP	PA
WL	1											
CON	-.336**	1										
REW	-.041	.518**	1									
COM	-.143	.683**	.470**	1								
FAIR	-.040	.513**	.568**	.680**	1							
VAL	-.153	.666**	.395**	.692**	.550**	1						
ST	-.117	-.062	-.280**	-.148	-.328**	-.161	1					
ANX	-.075	-.164	-.387**	-.231**	-.313**	-.178*	.834**	1				
DEP	-.201*	-.049	-.229**	-.108	-.220*	-.048	.682**	.716**	1			
EE	-.199*	-.052	-.394**	-.192*	-.340**	-.111	.571**	.452**	.365**	1		
DP	-.099	-.067	-.258**	-.106	-.128	.006	.346**	.348**	.300**	.694**	1	
PA	.013	.418**	.390**	.352**	.284**	.183*	-.093	-.182*	-.163	-.015	-.165	1

Workload (WL), Control (CON), Reward (REW), Community (COM), Fairness (FAIR), Values (VAL), Stress (ST), Anxiety (ANX), Depression (DEP), Emotional exhaustion (EE), Depersonalization (DP), Professional achievement (PA)

Analysis of correlations between mental health and job burnout indicates conclusively that teachers in Thailand and Indonesia who experience stress, anxiety, and depression are likely to develop emotional depletion, disconnection, and lack of effectiveness at work the findings are consistent with existing research and studies on burnout [30]–[32]. Burnout is recognized as a stress-related problem in interpersonally oriented occupations, such as teaching and healthcare [3], whereas persistent stress is a factor that increases the likelihood of various mental illnesses, such as anxiety and depression [33]. Moreover, burnout and depression have common symptoms.

To illustrate, the emotional exhaustion of burnout is similar to the sadness and fatigue of depression, and a component of depression, particularly low self-efficacy, has characteristics with the reduced personal achievement of burnout [34]. For that reason, burnout and depression are positively correlated, especially the association between emotional exhaustion and depression [35]. As stress, anxiety, depression, and job burnout have significant effects on teachers' physical and psychological well-being, job satisfaction, professional performance, and intentions to quit teaching profession [5], it is crucial to understand the relationships between these variables to highlight teachers' public health concerns and develop interventions to prevent teachers' mental health problems.

The results regarding the correlations between worklife areas, mental health, and burnout show a variation between Thai and Indonesian samples. In the case of Thai teachers, all six areas of work condition are strongly related to each dimension of mental health and burnout, while workload and fairness have significant relationships with stress, anxiety, depression, emotional depletion, and depersonalization. The findings highlight the significance of working conditions for Thai teachers' mental health concerns. Accordingly, school administrators and policymakers in Thailand must pay particular attention to teachers' worklife factors, which including job demands, autonomy at work, job resources, workplace equity, intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, and a conflict between teachers and the workplace, and foster a work environment that promotes their well-being.

In the case of Indonesian teachers, different areas of worklife are associated with each dimension of mental health and burnout to varying degrees. It is worth noting that rewards are strongly linked to all dimensions of mental health and burnout, whereas workload, control, community, fairness, and values are strongly linked to specific dimensions. It suggests that, to enhance the mental health of Indonesian teachers, special emphasis should be devoted to the balance between the rewards and efforts they get for their profession. However, other workplace factors should not be neglected because they also contribute to teachers' mental health issues.

As demonstrated in Table 5, Thai and Indonesian teachers exhibit distinct prediction patterns for several aspects of their professional lives. For Thai teachers, control and workload are significant predictors ($b=-1.799$, $p<.001$) and the model significantly explains 19.00% of the variance in stress in Thailand. Community and control are significant predictors ($b=-2.165$, $p<.001$) and the model significantly explains 17.50% of the variance in anxiety. Control together with reward are significant predictors ($b=-2.069$, $p<.001$) and the model significantly explains 25.40% of the variance in depression. Control, fairness, workload, and values are significant predictors ($b=-.331$, $p<.001$), and the model significantly explains 34.20% of the variance in emotional exhaustion. Community together with values are significant predictors ($b=-.290$, $p<.001$), and the model significantly explains 19.50% of the variance in depersonalization. Control and community are significant predictors ($b=-.347$, $p<.001$), and the model significantly explains 23.40% of the variance in depersonalization.

In Indonesia, fairness is a significant predictor ($b=-.570$, $p<.001$) and the model significantly explains 10.80% of the variance in stress, reward is a significant predictor ($b=-.500$, $p<.001$) and the model significantly explains 15.00% of the variance in anxiety, and reward together with workload are significant predictors ($b=-.268$, $p<.01$) and the model significantly explains 9.70% of the variance in depression. Reward and workload together are significant predictors ($b=-.427$, $p<.001$), and the model significantly explains 20.20% of the variance in emotional exhaustion. Reward is significant predictors ($b=-.336$, $p<.01$), and the model significantly explains 6.60% of the variance in depersonalization. Last but not least, control is significant predictors ($b=.643$, $p<.001$), and the model significantly explains 17.50% of the variance in personal accomplishment.

As for the influence of worklife factors on the mental health and job burnout of teachers in Thailand and Indonesia, despite the predictive patterns being distinct across the two groups, research findings from both countries supports the job demands-resources model (JD-R model), indicating that job demands, particularly workload, are a major risk factor of stress and exhaustion, whereas job resources, such as autonomy or control over the work, social support or community, and financial and social rewards are significant factors of cynicism and professional efficacy [28], [36]. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that the JD-R model may describe behaviors that occur in the workplace regardless of culture. To prevent and reduce teachers' mental health issues and job burnout, educational organizations in Thailand and Indonesia

must pay more attention to the areas of worklife, particularly workload, autonomy, social support, compensation, recognition of their work success, fairness, and meeting the needs or goals of the work in accordance with teachers' expectations.

Table 5. Forward multiple regression analysis

	Predictors	b	SE	Beta	R ²	F
Stress	Thailand					
	(Constant)	30.283	2.615			
	Control	-3.227	.630	-.333		
	Workload	-1.799	.568	-.206	.190	24.288***
	Indonesia					
Anxiety	(Constant)	3.258	.504			
	Fairness	-.570	.145	-.328	.108	15.439***
	Thailand					
	(Constant)	26.984	3.150			
	Community	2.985-	902.	242.-		
Depression	Control	2.165-	660.	240.-	.175	21.970***
	Indonesia					
	(Constant)	2.847	.420			
	Reward	-.500	.105	-.387	.150	22.585***
	Thailand					
Emotional exhaustion	(Constant)	24.900	2.309			
	Control	3.122-	.540	-.359		
	Reward	2.069-	.470	-.273	.254	35.237***
	Indonesia					
	(Constant)	2.446	.509			
Depersonalization	Reward	-.241	.086	-.238		
	Workload	-.268	.108	-.211	.097	6.801**
	Thailand					
	(Constant)	7.283	548.			
	Control	454.-	122.	251.-		
Personal accomplishment	Fairness	333.-	134.	172.-		
	Workload	403.-	105.	248.-		
	Values	331.-	156.	154.-	342.	26.609***
	Indonesia					
	(Constant)	4.985	.743			
Depersonalization	Reward	-.635	.125	-.403		
	Workload	-.427	1.57	-.216	202.	16.075***
	Thailand					
	(Constant)	4.284	.490			
	Community	-.595	.130	-.325		
Personal accomplishment	Values	-.290	.113	-.182	195.	25.123***
	Indonesia					
	(Constant)	1.987	.445			
	Reward	-.336	.111	-.258	066.	9.108**
	Thailand					
Personal accomplishment	(Constant)	1.077	444.			
	Community	529.	127.	294.		
	Control	347.	093.	263.	234.	31.557***
	Indonesia					
	(Constant)	1.608	.466			
Personal accomplishment	Control	.643	.123	.418	175.	27.103***

4. CONCLUSION

Teaching profession involves a huge strain owing to many demands. Teachers hence have significant risk to have mental health problems, notably stress, depression, anxiety, and burnout. As a result, teachers may consider leaving their profession. To support teachers' professional effectiveness, it is vital that organization recognizes all risk factors impacting teachers' mental health concerns. According to the current study, teachers in Thailand and Indonesia had comparable mean scores in six areas of worklife; however, their mental health and job burnout scores were distinct. In addition, it was demonstrated that the working conditions of teachers in Thailand and Indonesia may predict their mental health and job burnout. However, the expected patterns differed for each mental health scale and burnout level, as well as across the two groups. The findings shed light on the impact of workplace conditions on the mental health of teachers. Administrators of educational institutions and organizations interested in the promotion and development of teachers can utilize the data to build and implement policies and programs that match the requirements of specific persons.

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